

WERKSTOFFKUNDE UND
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ESTIMATION OF THE LIFE TIME OF 3D-PRINTED CONTINUOUS FIBER-REINFORCED COMPONENTS

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Agenda

Introduction – Life time estimation for sfr IM

Modified/extended methodology for AM

- Process simulation
- Temperature history – welding time – strength
- Life time simulation

Conclusion and outlook

Introduction

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CAD-Model:

Model discretization:

- Load definition
- Boundaries
- ...

Mapping: transfer of

- local fibre orientation
- Residual stresses
- ...

Results:

- Local stress
- Local strain
- ...

Solver

Material definition:

- – depending on fibre orientation
- Non-linear material behaviour

Introduction – Life time estimation for sfr IM

Results form FE:

- Local stress
- Local strain
- ...

From process-simulation:

- Local fibre orientation
- Position of weld lines

Test data / models:

- Combined in a dataset

Results:

- Local damage / life time
- Local S/N curve
- ...

FEMFAT software
FINITE ELEMENT METHOD FATIGUE

Solver: includes

- Material models
- Damage accumulation

Model:

- Load scaling
- Material assingment

Modified/extended methodology for AM

Modified/extended methodology for AM

Process simulation

Inputs:
 printing path;
 part geometry;
 thermal material properties;
 nozzle temperature;
 strand parameters; ...

Deposition path

Orientation

Life time simulation

Temperature history - welding time - strength

Printing of walls with different nozzle temperatures
 $(T_{n1}, T_{n2}, T_{n3}, T_{n4})$

↑ Mechanical testing
 Determination of weld strength σ
 ↓

T-measurement during printing
 Determination of welding time τ

higher welding time τ
 higher strength σ

Process simulation

FE-model

Thermo couple (0.08mm)

Temperature history – welding time – strength

Processing at different nozzle temperatures (T_n)

- T_{n1}
- T_{n2}
- T_{n3}

Mechanical test specimen → strength (quasistatic, fatigue)

- σ_1
- σ_2
- σ_3

T-profile (IR cam, thermoelements) → welding time

- T_1
- T_2
- T_3

strength vs. welding time

equivalent isothermal weld time
[J. Seppala, Soft Matter 2017]

τ = areas above T_g weighted by $1/a_T$
(temperature shift factor - chain mobility)

Temperature history – welding time – fatigue data

R = 0.1 / -1
f = 5 Hz

Validation via demonstrator

- Validation of specimen data on demonstrator level

- Temperature simulation of demonstrator

- Fatigue test on demonstrator with $R=0.1$, $f=1\text{Hz}$

Conclusion and outlook

Conclusion and outlook

- Determine effect of **thermal history** and **fiber orientation** on **weld strength** → temperature and orientation dependent model
- Thermo-mechanical coupled process simulation to evaluate welding time → possibility to evaluate **mechanical behavior for each node** in a part volume
- **Validation via demonstrator**
 - Simulation of thermal history and fiber orientation
 - Femfat based lifetime estimation based on local properties
 - Comparison to actual lifetime of tested demonstrator

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